

Power modulator for broadband agile mirror radar utilizing semiconductor switching

M. C. Myers, R. F. Fernsler, J. A. Gregor, J. Mathew,
R. A. Meger, D. P. Murphy, and R. E. Pechacek

Plasma Physics Division, Code 6750

Naval Research Laboratory, Washington, D.C. 20375-5346

Power modulators have been designed which can generate fast rising, high voltage pulses up to 10 kV with arbitrary pulse widths at pulse repetition frequencies greater than 5 kHz. The design utilizes series IGBT switching. The modulators drive the NRL Agile Mirror experiment - an electronically steered sheet plasma which can be used to direct a microwave beam for radar and communications applications.

Introduction

A sheet plasma of sufficient density can be used to direct a microwave beam for radar and communications applications.¹ Such a "plasma mirror" is generated using high voltage, fast rise time, variable width pulses at high pulse repetition frequencies (PRF). In addition, the plasma mirror must be steerable or agile in both azimuth and altitude. The Agile Mirror Experiment at NRL has produced a planar 60 x 60 cm sheet plasma capable of directing X-band microwaves.² The present modulator design uses a Crossatron³ as the primary switching element. Although the Crossatron is rugged and reliable, it is also very expensive and the typical voltage drop across the tube approaches 500 Volts. The next generation Agile Mirror requires multiple modulators to drive a cathode array to demonstrate azimuthal agility. Thus, it is desirable and cost effective to consider power semiconductor switching as an alternative. The insulated gate bipolar transistor (IGBT) was chosen for this application due to its high current capacity and high frequency capability at voltages of 1.2-1.6 kV. Since several kilovolts are needed to generate the sheet plasma, a series connection of IGBTs is required. The

switching design includes careful consideration of voltage sharing in steady state and during the switching transient as well as gate drive circuit and thermal issues.

Agile Mirror Experiment

A plasma distribution presents an interesting way to direct electromagnetic waves. Since the plasma is effectively without inertia, it can in principle be electronically steered to illuminate and receive with great agility (*i.e.* it can be formed in one location to reflect a radar beam for targeting, turned off for a short duration, and then reformed in another orientation for receiving the radar echo). The distribution also provides broadband and high power handling capability. To reflect incident electromagnetic radiation, a plasma must have a density greater than the critical density $n_c = m_e \epsilon_0 \omega^2 / e^2$. For incident X-band (8.2-12.4 GHz) microwaves, $n_c \approx 1.2 \times 10^{12} \text{ cm}^{-3}$. The distribution must be reproducible and have a size which is large compared to the longest wavelength used while being flat on a scale length smaller than the shortest wavelength used.

The NRL Agile Mirror is a 60 x 60 cm plasma sheet distribution created in a vacuum chamber at pressures of 100-200 mTorr.

Figure 1 illustrates the experimental layout. The distribution is magnetically confined to a 1 cm thickness by a set of Helmholtz coils which generate a 200 Gauss axial field. The plasma is generated by a high voltage pulse modulator⁴ which drives an abnormal glow discharge between a hollow cathode and a planar anode. The discharge voltage can be as high as 8 kV and the discharge impedance is about 300 Ω near critical density.

FIG. 1. Experimental configuration.

For radar and communications applications, the pulse modulator must be capable of producing square voltage pulses with variable pulse duration and duty cycle. The plasma distribution requires up to 8 kV and 30 A. The Agile Mirror modulator was designed to output a maximum of ten 500 μ s wide pulses every second with a maximum voltage droop of 15%. It can also operate in a burst mode where pulse trains of arbitrary duration and PRF are produced. Figure 2 shows the plasma voltage wave form for an eight pulse burst of 500 μ s pulses at 1 kHz. A Crossatron provides primary switching at a voltage rating of 25 kV. The peak anode current is 500 A with a maximum average current rating of 0.25 A. The Crossatron can be operated in burst mode up to 500 kHz. These specifications are well above the design requirements.

Experimental results to date have shown promise in using the plasma mirror as microwave beam director. The plasma

distribution is very reproducible and has demonstrated broadband capability at high power levels. A 10 GHz beam reflected 90° has a very similar far field radiation pattern as one reflected by a metal plate and is comparable to the radiation pattern produced by the illuminating dish alone.² The critical surface of the plasma remains essentially stationary moving less than 0.2 mm over a 1 ms time scale². Preliminary experiments using an auxiliary magnetic field to tilt the plasma distribution and control the elevation of the directed beam have succeeded in angling the plasma $\pm 22.5^\circ$ while maintaining the integrity of the distribution.

Experiments to demonstrate azimuthal agility propose an array of cathodes which are individually pulsed. Depending on the desired beam direction, a "row" of cathodes would be designated to form the plasma in a given orientation. After a short time, another set of cathodes would be pulsed to direct the beam along another azimuth. Several pulse modulators may be required for this effort. In the interest of economics and system complexity, the use of power semiconductors as the primary switching element must be considered.

FIG. 2. Plasma voltage for eight pulse burst.

IGBT Switched Modulator

As a less expensive, less complex alternative to the Crossatron, IGBTs were chosen to serve as the primary switching

element for the cathode array experiments. IGBTs have high current capability with low ohmic losses and can be gated at high frequency using a low voltage. For a plasma mirror of dimension 1 m and density $n_e \sim 10^{12}$, up to 10 kV and 35 A may be required at the pulse durations and PRF previously outlined. Commercial IGBTs are available with a $V_{CES} \approx 0.6$ -1.6 kV in a wide range of currents. Higher voltage ratings compromise switching rise times due to internal device structure. To meet the voltage requirements, at least 10 IGBTs are required in a series connection. Figure 3 is a schematic of the basic circuit. There are only a few references available on the series connection of IGBTs for high voltage switching.⁵⁻⁸ The papers by Letor and Palmer provide some design guidance while the others outline experimental applications. Consideration must be given to voltage regulation in the steady state and during the switching transient and to circuit design in terms of layout, protection, and thermal management.

Since the modulator may be operated at low frequency and duty cycle as well as in burst mode, steady state voltage balance must be considered. Component variations inherent in manufacturing result in blocking voltage differences. With varying leakage currents the supply voltage V_S may be unequally shared by the series IGBTs. A parallel resistor network can be used to balance the voltages preventing any single component from being overstressed. A conservative value of the resistor that may be used in the network is given by,

$$R_b = (0.9nV_{CES} - V_s) / (\Delta I_{CES}(n-1)) \quad (1)$$

where n is the number of IGBTs in series and ΔI_{CES} is the maximum difference in leakage current.⁵ The value of ΔI_{CES} is dependent on the junction temperature of each device. At high operating temperatures, the leakage current can be substantial. It is therefore

important to keep the IGBT junction temperature differences small by mounting them to the same heat sink. In any case, we can take $\Delta I_{CES} \approx 0.85 I_{CES}$.⁵ For example, if an IXYS (type IXSK35N120AU1) IGBT is used $V_{CES} = 1.2$ kV and $I_{CES} (@90^\circ\text{C}) = 10$ mA. With $V_S = 10$ kV and $n = 10$ for the application, equation (1) gives $R \approx 10$ k Ω for the worst case analysis.

The supply voltage must be equally shared by the IGBTs during the switching transient. There are two basic approaches to gating a series connection of IGBTs: i) driving each IGBT in series with synchronized pulses and masking delay times using snubber capacitors or ii) equalizing switching times with an optimized driving circuit using capacitive coupling between output and driving circuits.⁵ The former can be accomplished with careful control of the driving and coupling circuits. For the wide range of pulse widths required for the agile mirror, transformer coupling is difficult. However, Fuji Electronics makes a gate driver (type EXB840) which is optimized for the IGBT and uses optical isolation greatly simplifying driving circuit. Synchronization of gate pulses within 5 ns has been achieved.⁷ A single gate pulse can be used to switch all stages in succession by using capacitive

FIG. 3. Schematic of basic circuit.

coupling. A capacitor is connected from the gate of IGBT #2 to the emitter of the first IGBT in the chain with the successive gates linked by a parallel diode and capacitor. Assuming all capacitor voltages are balanced, when the gate pulse is applied, the first IGBT turns on pulling down the emitter of the second. The capacitor then charges the gate of the second IGBT and the process repeats up the ladder.⁵ A regulator for each gate may be necessary for better switching performance.⁶ For the agile mirror, the brute force simplicity of synchronized pulses is attractive but both methods of gating will be explored.

Since the switching element will be operated in a pulsed power environment, it must be protected against voltage surges and EMI influences. During the turn-off phase, a switching voltage is induced in the main circuit due to stray inductances. A circuit layout which minimizes stray inductance is thus desirable and snubber circuit for overvoltage protection may be required. The snubber circuit is designed to keep the switching surge voltage below the IGBT breakdown voltage. The most practical snubber for the application may be a charge-discharge RCD circuit since the device will not be operated at very high frequency and losses in the snubber resistance are tolerable.⁹ The use of Zener diodes and metal oxide varistors to protect the IGBT and driving circuit against voltage spikes may be necessary.

Conclusions

A power modulator which utilizes series IGBT switching has been designed. Careful consideration of voltage sharing and device protection is required. The semiconductor switched modulator provides a more desirable, less expensive alternative to tube switched modulators for driving a cathode array for a sheet plasma discharge.

Acknowledgments

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